

D3.2 – The fundamentals of the mobility culture of today

A critical analysis on current travel patterns and emerging
mobility values

Work Package:	WP3
Deliverable:	D3.2
Due date:	July 2021
Submission date:	November 2021
Responsible Partner:	TUD / UNIZA
Version:	Final
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Deliverable Type:	R
Dissemination Level:	PU

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Executive Summary

REBALANCE moves from the assumption that the mobility culture that currently prevails in the world (including Europe) has led to unsustainable travel patterns, in social and environmental terms. The mobility choices made by users, fall short of ensuring a sustainable balance between traffics and places, freedom and welfare, creativity, security and public health. Therefore, there is a need for a critical examination in particular of the meaning and value(s) of European mobility culture of today.

The objective of this report is to look deeper into the question, which values do travellers express currently? Through that it contributes to the whole picture of mobility culture with covering individual aspects of people in their mobility behaviour. A critical examination will be made of the meaning, value, and impacts of mobility of today through a cross-European analysis of selected travel patterns (in particular mode choice) and mobility values (e.g. perceived value of time) with a particular focus on gender and generational conflicts. The value expression analysis can be done mainly on two levels: Firstly, on a behavioural level and secondly, on an attitudinal level. However, it has to be mentioned that besides a few academic papers which directly assessed mobility values or motives most of the studies available do not assess values directly. Thus, in both cases one has to infer either from the observed behaviour or the measured attitude whether it is value-based and in what direction.

The analysis of individual value orientations in the European Union based on data of the European Social Study (ESS, 2018) reveals even though countries show variations in their individual value structure, an overall "European" pattern. In particular, all countries show overall a strong emphasis on power and stimulation. Hedonism and achievement as well as conformity add to the important values among Europeans. Value orientations towards security, benevolence and universalism reach in most countries no positive mean and accordingly play a minor role in the European society.

Then, an in-depth-analysis about the expression of values in mode choice is carried out. Unsurprisingly, using a car is very common in EU. More than at least 71% of the daily trip-kilometres are made by car with some variation between countries. The more environmentally friendly modes like bicycle or public transport (PT) play a much lesser role with huge variations between countries, age groups and spatial conditions. However, in the long-term car traffic has plateaued or decreased in the last decade or more, after many decades of more or less continuous growth in several industrialized countries ("peak car"). Reasons mentioned in the academic discussion for the observed trend break are economic growth, fuel price but also alternative explanations like e.g. a shift away from car use in urban areas, increased road congestion, restrictive car policies and a permanent change in attitudes and preferences of users.

Looking at the motivations behind mode choice convenience was found to be a main motivator independent from the actual mode and for all genders and ages, whereas speed shows more importance among men than among women (34% vs 28%) and more for young and middle-aged adults. Even though traveling costs are perceived by the majority as an important problem among 24 member states, it is behind the other three motivators. All modes of transport have in these categories different strengths and weaknesses. Most of the car users for instance, drive because of convenience (72%) and speed considerations (42%). Half of the PT-users, pedestrians and cyclists as well choose their main mode of transport for convenience reasons. Price considerations matter for about a quarter of bicycle and PT-users and cyclists are additionally motivated by the speed and environmental reasons. In the overall means environmental considerations matter recognisable only for the decision to cycle (22% of the bicycle users). Nevertheless, on-going research shows, that environmental

awareness has risen in the last years. Climate change is considered as one of the most serious problems the world is facing nowadays. Additionally, it is very likely that the perception of convenience has changed, in particular due to the rise of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and therefore the diverse additional options to enjoy travel time and make it worthwhile. However, an in-depth analysis of a Belgium sample (de Vos, 2018) reveals that only half of the respondents were able to choose their preferred mode of transport. The concept of not using the subjectively preferred mode is called 'Travel mode dissonance' and may lead to dissatisfaction with the chosen mode. Interestingly cyclists made the most congruent choices. More than half of the car users and pedestrians would prefer using another mode of transport with many of them see more positive sides in traveling by bike. Travel mode dissonance appears to be the biggest problem among users of PT.

Regarding possible changes in attitudes among young people towards car use findings from relevant studies show a mixed but falling trend in driver license acquisition in most EU countries. Results indicate a mixture of economic, structural (e.g. household conditions, delayed marriage and parenting) and attitude/value-based reasons (e.g. rather responsibility than freedom). In addition, a recent US study shows that millennials are more willing to use multimodal transport modes compared to older generations.

With regard to the negative consequences of car use a majority of Europeans (74% in 2007) thinks, that the type and usage of cars significantly influences the traffic situation in their environment, but environmental considerations are overall only a minor reason for mode choice behaviour. As well, there are even more people (90%), that agree on the fact, that the traffic situation needs to be improved and motorized traffic related environmental problems are by about 70% of the Europeans perceived as very important or fairly important problems – with one exception Finland. Half of them find that an improved public transport can solve these problems. A willingness to switch to more sustainable modes of transport is in the majority present, but only if it is not more expensive. Additionally, it is supposed to be fast and available. Most willing were younger people with higher education level and rather leftist political position in urban environments.

In a case study based on data of the MoTiV project the effect of the perception of value of travel time and value of ridesharing on Europeans' ridesharing intentions is investigated. The study results demonstrate that most people prefer to adopt ridesharing for work compared to other trip purposes. In this case, 21% of all respondents are willing to share their rides only with family or friends and 36% of respondents are willing to adopt ridesharing when commuting to/from work even with strangers. People prefer to share the rides for the purpose of hobby or leisure during the weekend. Only 21% of respondents are willing to adopt ridesharing during evening trips which may be due to the perception of reduced safety mainly. This survey results also show that the biggest motivator for respondents to share a ride is cost saving or financial benefit (35%). The other two important motivators are easier travel (24%) and helping the environment (22%). In addition, in the MoTiV project, the value of travel time (VTT) has been assessed based on individuals' subjective travel experience using different transport modes and the evaluation of the perceived level of worthwhileness and perceived mood during trip. Results of a reanalysis elucidate that for all the worthwhileness elements, the majority of people travelling by motorized mode transport reported enjoyment and ability to do personal task while on move as the most important gained value for their travel time. As expected for the active modes, men and women reported fitness (ability to exercise) as the most worthwhile value perceived during travel time. Furthermore, positive and negative experience factors reported by users affecting the perceived value of travel time have been identified. Interestingly, quite a few of the reported positive experience factors relate to transport

services and infrastructure such as the road path availability, quality and directness, reliability, parking, information and signs or route planning and navigation tools.

The role and importance of ICT in mobility has been investigated from different perspectives and in various disciplines. There is a considerable evidence that digital personal devices strongly influence mobility and activity patterns of individuals across cultures, generations and gender. The detailed impact of ICT on mobility (in particular with regard to age, gender and mode use) is reanalysed with data from the EU projects MoTiV and MyCorridor. Results show differences among different gender and age ranges in terms of using online journey planners as well as the frequency and type of ICT related activities. With regard to the question which ICT-related activities lead to the travellers' perception of travel time satisfaction and worthwhileness, reading on electronic devices was perceived as the most worthwhile ICT related activity. However, when comparing the results based on age groups, there is a significant difference in evaluating worthwhileness. Finally, we look if the pandemic urged travellers to substitute their travel needs by using telecommunication. However, so far only anecdotal evidence exists. A recent study on the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on Italian young people's lifestyle and leisure activities reveals a significant increase in online participation in a variety of activities by the youngest age group. The study results also accentuated the higher interest of female respondents in participation in webinars or online tutorials, using social media and messaging services and communication through chat and video-chatting services while males were more interested in playing online games.

1 INTRODUCTION

Transport is not only an important prerequisite for the functionality and economic performance of modern societies, it also plays a central role in individual life (e.g. leisure time, social inclusion). The dramatic growth in transport demands over the past few decades has led to numerous negative social, ecological and economic consequences. Traffic is a major cause of air pollution, noise pollution, land consumption and landscape fragmentation. A large part of the CO₂ emissions, the most important greenhouse gas with an climate impact, can be traced back to the energy consumption in the transport sector (30% of the EU's total CO₂ emissions), with 72 % of the road traffic being the main cause within the transport sector (EEA, 2019). Passenger cars are a major polluter, accounting for 60.7% of total CO₂ emissions from road transport in Europe. The several negative consequences of road transport not only affect people and the environment, they also cause enormous economic damage in the form of external costs.

REBALANCE moves from the assumption that the mobility culture that currently prevails in the world (including Europe) has led to unsustainable travel patterns, in social and environmental terms. The mobility choices made by users, fall short of ensuring a sustainable balance between traffics and places, freedom and welfare, creativity, security and public health. Therefore, there is a need for a critical examination in particular of the meaning and value(s) of European mobility culture of today.

In Deliverable 3.1. the theoretical framework for the description and investigation of mobility culture was developed. To conceptualize mobility culture and to identify relevant factors within the REBALANCE analysis, a culture model of mobility developed by Deffner et al. (2006) was applied and extended, which combines subjective and objective factors in order to measure the characteristics of mobility cultures. Within the model four interactive dimensions of mobility culture are identified as a spatial (including technology), an individual subjective, that will be covered in this report, a communicative (see Deliverable 3.4) and a political dimension (see Deliverable 3.3) that have been successively extended to be applicable to a cross-national scope. Whereas the four dimensions in the mobility culture framework are useful for the description of cultural expressions, all elements of (mobility) culture discussed have one thing in common: They are all guided by basic values (and related constructs like e.g. attitudes, beliefs, motifs and goals). The basic values as stated by Schwartz (1992) can be organised according to their motivational goals they express along two dimensions: egoism vs. altruism and individualism vs. conformism.

Travellers' subjective motivations for mode choice revealed in particular egoistic (or instrumental) motives (like comfort, safety, cost, time), conformist (or social-symbolic) motives (like e.g. communication of status, prestige superiority, power), and individualistic (or intrinsic- affective) motives (like freedom of choice, feeling of independence a.s.o.). However, altruistic motives (like enhancement of the welfare of people, protecting the environment), which correspond in particular to sustainable mobility goals, have been largely not considered.

Thus, the objective of this report is to look deeper into the question, which values do travellers express currently? Through that it contributes to the whole picture of mobility culture with covering individual aspects of people in their mobility behaviour. A critical examination will be made of the meaning, value, and impacts of mobility of today through a cross-European analysis of current travel patterns (in particular mode choice) and mobility values (e.g. perceived value of time) with a particular focus on gender and generational conflicts. The value expression analysis can be done mainly on two levels: Firstly, on a behavioural level and secondly, on an attitudinal level. It has to be mentioned that besides a few academic papers which directly assessed mobility values or motives (e.g. Gatersleben & Uzzell, 2007; Steg, 2005) most of the studies available

do not assess values directly. Thus, in both cases one has to infer either from the observed behaviour or the measured attitude whether it is value-based and in what direction. This includes necessarily a subjective component, which leaves at least partly some interpretable space.

The report is organized as follows: Firstly, we will analyse based on data of the European Social Study (ESS) individual value orientations in the European Union and try to identify whether there is one European value pattern. Then, an in-depth-analysis about the expression of values in mode choice is carried out. A comparison is made between the actual mode share in EU and the motivations behind the choices as stated by travellers as well as hidden motives which are often ignored. In a case study based on data of the MoTiV project it will be investigated, whether the perception of value of travel time and value of ridesharing affects Europeans' ridesharing intentions. In addition, positive and negative experience factors reported by users affecting the perceived value of travel time are identified. Finally, the impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on mobility is reanalysed with data from the EU projects MoTiV and MyCorridor.

2 INDIVIDUAL VALUE ORIENTATIONS IN EUROPEAN UNION

The most profound influence of values may be through the ways that they influence rules, norms, procedures within a society, and in this way structure the everyday life choices for individuals within a society (see D3.1). Values at the individual level or personal values have been defined as "*broad, trans-situational, desirable goals, varying in importance, that serve as guiding principles in people's lives*" (Schwartz, 1992). Ten basic human values have been identified that are cross-culturally replicated which can be organized more generally in a two-dimensional space, both with two conflicting poles: egoism versus altruism and individualism versus conformism. As a starting point of analysis, an overview over most common individual European values should be given, in order to build a base for analysis of the current mobility behaviour and motivations.

The two most prominent data sources, from which direct statements about (European) values can be made, are the European Values Study (EVS) and the European Social Study (ESS). The European Values Study (EVS), initiated in 1978, theoretically follows Ingelhard's post-materialism approach and value priority concept. The EVS covers a wide range of human values that are related to fields like life, family, politics, environment and society (Bréchon & Gonthier, 2017). The data is rather old (2008), because the last data collection from 2017-2021 is not available yet.

Secondly, the European Social Study (ESS), which started in 2001, examines attitudes, beliefs and behaviour patterns concerning social and political topics and follows an academic driven approach. The ESS questionnaire includes a well-established 21-item measure of human values, which was developed by Schwartz. The 'Human Values Scale' is designed to classify respondents according to their basic value orientations. The Human Values Scale has been included in every ESS round to date. In face-to-face interviews, more than 30 nations are examined every two years. All data is available free of charge and the study is jointly funded by all participating countries. The latest round (9) was run in 2018 and the data released in February 2021. Looking deeper into the shared set of values, we analysed the data from the ESS Round 9 (2018).

Figure 1 shows a diagram of the mean value orientations of European countries from the ESS 2018 following the circle of basic values by Schwartz (1991). Even though countries show variations in their individual value structure, where a detailed analysis

would go far beyond the scope of this project, an overall “European” pattern comes to light. In the down right quarter of the net, where the egoistic (Power, Achievement, Pleasure) and individual values (Self-Direction and Stimulation) are grouped, the amplitudes are very high. In particular all countries show overall a strong emphasis on power and stimulation. Hedonism and achievement as well as conformity add to the important values among Europeans. Value orientations towards security, benevolence and universalism reach in most countries no positive mean and accordingly play a minor role in the European society.

Figure 1: Mean European Values over EU-28. Centred means of all respondents per country; N = 49,519 (Own analysis, Source: ESS 2018).

Apart of representative European surveys on individual value orientations, a Standard Eurobarometer about the cultural values of Europeans has been done in 2012. The major difference between individual (like in ESS) and cultural values (like in EUROBAROMETER) is, that individual values are part of the personality and the latter refers to normative aspects and are rather external of individuals (Schwartz, 2011). In sum the Eurobarometer data show, that Europeans share by great national variations similar views on some values like e.g. human rights, peace, respect for the environment which are also considered as being more European than universal. In addition, the usual conflicts between e.g. the economy and the environment or equality vs. self-fulfilment become apparent.

The authors also emphasize a change in individual values over time (e.g. the decrease in the importance of the environment between 2007 and 2013) and attribute this primarily to the consequences of the economic crisis of 2008. This development is in particular interesting when considering the development of the years after this Eurobarometer, where ecological and environmental considerations entered political and societal debates and induced some fundamental changes in European decisions. The changes illustrate the, in D3.1 introduced, theory of materialist-vs.-postmaterialist values as stated by Inglehart (1997). Accordingly, post-material needs are usually not considered before material needs (physiological and safety needs) are satisfied. With fundamental threads on economical and social welfare due to the financial crisis,

environmental concerns may fade into the background if they are considered rather post-materialist. After the rising awareness towards fundamental threads of a global warming, it is likely that people started considering environment-related needs as relevant for basic material needs. How much these tendencies can be found in mobility decisions of Europeans remains difficult to assess on a European level. What studies on a European level have in common is, that those analysing general values over EU don't leave the possibility to connect them directly with mobility behaviour and those analysing mobility do rarely include measures on values. Therefore, in the following the benchmarking of the mobility cultures in EU should be seen as narrations or as a rather indirect deduction, that are not fully empirically based.

3 THE EXPRESSION OF VALUES IN MODE CHOICE

Mode choice is a highly habituated decision. As stated in D3.1, different modes of transport can fulfill various motives for their users. Not only instrumental motives like reaching from point A to point B but also affective (emotional) and symbolic motives can be connected with the chosen means of transport. Cars are the most criticized mode of transport when it comes to environmental concerns not only because of their emissions and noise pollution but also because of space scarcity in urban areas. A whole industry tries to develop towards more sustainability to meet the new demands of a more environmental concerned society. Nevertheless, not only in urban areas many other modes of transport are highly relevant for daily mobility of people. Public Transport (PT) as a mass-transportation service, active modes like cycling and walking and more recently micromobility modes like electric scooters come along with more multimodality options – the opportunity to combine different modes for a seamless mobility chain. All this raise the question what made the car to the dominant mode as it still is nowadays. In the following chapter the use of modes will be reflected and in the next step the different motives and values that may explain the current modal share analyzed.

3.1 The modal share in European Union

Figure 2: Share of person-kilometres per day that are realized by car. Source: EUROSTATS, 2019

Using a car is the most common way to fulfil daily travel needs of Europeans. More than at least 71% of the daily trip-kilometers are made by car with some variation between countries as expressed in Figure 2. Whereas some countries lead the statistics with over 86% of car usage, especially East European countries show relatively lower shares (e.g. Hungary with 71%). Men still have a tendency to use a car more regularly, than women (57% vs. 42%). This very high level of car usage (Figure 2) and motorisation rate (Figure 3) are relatively stable over the last decade in the overall means in EU.

In the academic discussion this observed stagnating trend is referred to as 'Peak car'. It discusses the reasons why in several industrialized countries, car traffic has plateaued or decreased in the last decade or more, after many decades of more or less continuous growth (e.g. Metz, 2010 and 2013; Goodwin, 2013). The most interesting point is the question of what could have caused this trend break. Several authors have argued that standard explanatory variables such as economic growth and fuel price cannot explain it. Instead, it is referred to alternative explanations like e.g. a shift away from car use in urban areas, increased road congestion and restrictive car policies. However, the hypothesis which received the highest attention is that a permanent change in attitudes and preferences caused the downward trend in car driving and ownership (Bastian, Börjesson & Eliasson, 2016). As evidence for a lasting attitude change some authors mention a trend decline in younger people holding driving licenses (Delbosc and Currie, 2013; Kuhnimhof et al., 2012; Zhou & Wang, 2019) or the increased use of ICT van Wee, 2015). Both arguments will be analysed more in detail later in this report. However, the peak car hypothesis has not been unchallenged. E.g. Bastian et al. (2016) are able to explain the plateau and decrease in car traffic in six countries (United States, United Kingdom, France, Sweden, Australia and Germany) with a simple model based on GDP per capita and gasoline price. The discussion about possible reasons for the observed trends is ongoing and remains unanswered yet (Focas & Christidis, 2017). From a scientific viewpoint, most of the data used in the above papers is correlational which does not allow for causal conclusions.

Figure 3: Motorisation rate in European countries in 2019 (EUROSTATS, 2019)

The biggest differences between countries in mode choice is the **bicycle usage** (European Commission, 2014). Overall, the bicycle held in 2014 8% of the modal share in European Union, but only few countries like the Netherlands, Denmark, Hungary, Germany and Sweden seem to complement driving and public transport with a remarkable share of cyclists for transportation on a daily base. In countries e.g. Sweden, Hungary or the Netherlands, where people cycle on a daily base, the leisure cycling rates are rather low whereas in countries with a lower daily cycling rate (e.g. Spain, United Kingdom or Italy) people rather cycle as a leisure activity (Fraboni et al., 2021). Leisure cyclists cycle mostly for fun, hedonic and individual motives play a major role in choosing to cycle but they usually not use their bike as a means of transport. On the other hand, everyday cyclists mainly cycle because of instrumental reasons. Fraboni et al. (2021) referred to the latter group also as 'robust cyclists' and described them with a clear preference for bicycle compared to car use even when the bike is not the most comfortable mode to use. This division of use cases between transport motives and recreational fun can be found as well for the rising sector of micromobility modes. Even though representative mode choice analyses do not collect data on their mode share, yet, it can be found in various smaller national studies, that in particular electric scooters are more and more considered in mobility decisions. Still, they are mostly used from sharing services for fun or by tourists to get around, but a growing number uses them for daily trips (Deutscher Verkehrssicherheitsrat, 2020).

Public transport (PT) seems to complement car use, as the non-driver shares can be found mirrored in most countries in the PT-user shares (see Figure 4). Public transport

Figure 4: Share of person-kilometres that are realized by public transport (buses, motor coaches, trolley buses and trains). Source: EUROSTATS, 2019.

users are much more found in the age group between 15-24 years old (38%) with half of them studying. Using public transport is most common in Eastern areas of the EU (European Commission, 2019). There are huge differences between the accessibility of PT in urban and rural areas, mostly attributable to the economic situation of the population, political will and spatial prerequisites. Public transport is, even by regular users, often poorly rated with problems in coverage, frequency and reliability.

providers expanded in the last decade and are still growing, especially in Eastern Europe, where the trend emerged a little later (Rodenbach et al., 2020). Especially among the younger generation the usage of a shared car instead of owning one is much more common (Prieto, Baltas, and Stan, 2017).

In European Union individual mobility does not any more mean owning a vehicle. **Sharing service**

Accordingly, it should be asked if one needs to possess a mode of transport to feel personal values reflected? In particular the younger generation may see the car as a much more instrumental mode, that fulfills transport needs instead of showing status and possession (Miller, 2001). Other factors of driving, such as a perceived freedom and pleasure driving a car (or a bike) is not necessarily eliminated, if the vehicle is not possessed. Depending on the sharing concept, the freedom and flexibility of accessing always the mode that is most appropriate for the current demands could even produce stronger feelings of autonomy. Also negative side-effects of owning a vehicle the search for a free parking lot to leave the car or the responsibility for repairing our bike are omitted.

Ramos et al. (2020) found very different travel styles that consider car sharing as a useful extension of their set of mode choices. Along attitudes, social norms, preferences in mode choice and trip frequency per day, they found the following three user groups:

- "Multi mode – Low environmentalists": They use a private car on a medium level but may decide for a shared car if it is easier to access due to well located parking lots. They mostly use PT but have very low environmental concerns.
- "Car-focused Ambivalent": They have a strong habit towards private car use and choose only seldom the PT or active modes as an alternative. They are highest in environmental concerns.
- "Active PT-transport Green": They have very weak habits in private car use or even live car-free and usually rely on PT or active modes. Environmental concerns are very high, what is a main reason for them to use car-sharing.

Groups of people, that are not likely to use car-sharing are characterized as

- "Active PT-transport Green": They very seldomly use motorized vehicles and use PT or active modes for daily trips and have a very high environmental concern.
- "Car-focused Low-green": They use a car regularly and report low levels of environmental concern.

The appearance of high- and low environmental concerned people in the non-user and user group indicates, that sustainability considerations are not crucial when considering car sharing usage. But a car focused mobility style does not mean to not adopt car sharing. Car sharing seems to rather contribute to finding reflects again convenience motives. The authors give two interpretation approaches for the low environmental value impact of car sharing: Either people do not consider environmental issues in their transport choices or car sharing itself is not considered as environmental friendly because it still involves a certain level of air pollution and environmental harm (Ramos et al., 2020).

3.2 Motivations behind mode choice

The preference of different modes of transport is steered by different motivational aspects behind the need of being mobile and the how to be mobile. Taking all European countries together, as reported in the EUROBAROMETER (2014), the most important considerations here are convenience, speed and the availability of facilities.

Convenience was found to be a main motivator independent from the actual mode and for all genders and ages, whereas speed shows more importance among men than among women (34% vs 28%) and more for young and middle-aged adults. Even though traveling costs are perceived by the majority as an important problem among 24 member states, it is behind the other three motivators. All modes of transport have in

Figure 5: Reasons for using this mode of transport (Rotate, Max. 2 Answers). Base: Respondents who use a mode of transport (N=27,678). Own illustration, based on data from European Commission, (2014).

these categories different strengths and weaknesses (see Figure 5). Most of the car users for instance, drive because of convenience (72%) and speed considerations (42%) Half of the PT-users, pedestrians and cyclists as well choose their main mode of transport for convenience reasons. Price considerations matter for about a quarter of

bicycle and PT-users and cyclists are additionally motivated by the speed and environmental reasons. In the overall means environmental considerations matter recognisable only for the decision to cycle (22% of the bicycle users). Interestingly, a better and cheaper access to public transport is considered as a solution for urban congestion problems for many Europeans (59% wish lower prices, 56% better public transport) but also better cycling and walking facilities (33% and 28%) (European Commission, 2013). These preferences do not vary much between users of different modes. Restrictions or facilitations for car traffic seems to take a lower priority. Differences in local infrastructure and other mobility concerning circumstances may explain variances in preferences. Restrictions on the use of trucks in cities or encouragements to limit car use are for more than half of the Europeans a conceivable way to improve urban mobility.

Figure 6: All respondents of Special Eurobarometer 495 who have a daily or regular mobility (N=26,747). (Source: European Commission, 2020).

Even though the data is from 2014, the tendency of main usage motivations is rather stable since decades in the majority of the countries (European Commission, 2020). Nevertheless, research shows, that environmental awareness has risen in the last years. Climate change is considered as one of the most serious problems the world is facing nowadays. Additionally, it is very likely that the perception of convenience has changed, in particular due to the rise of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and therefore the diverse additional options to enjoy travel time and make it worthwhile. The effects of worthwhileness due to ICT will be discussed deeper in chapter 4.

Not surprisingly, these factors as well are the most considered, when it comes to their readiness to change to a less polluting mode of transport (European Commission, 2013). There seems to be a difference between generations in the weighting of the factors. Except of the middle European countries, comfort is the absolute leading factor for mode choice through all generations (Figure 6). Germany, Austria, Hungary, Slovakia and Czech Republic convenience is similarly rated like speed and price. These factors all follow instrumental goals.

3.2.1 THE IMPACT OF MOBILITY STYLES ON MOTIVATIONS FOR MODE CHOICE

A first glance in the diversity of how values influence mobility behaviour in the European Union is provided by Haustein et al. (2016). Based on data from the EUROBAROMETER they found eight different mobility styles with different representations in the EU member-states. Mobility styles are in different European studies used for multifactorial analysis of different mobility patterns. These styles are derived from different individual motivations towards mobility-related questions here for instance convenience, speed and price and different shares and the preferred mode of transport for daily trips.

Haustein and Nielsen found in their study almost half of the Europeans to be classified as "Convenient Drivers" (see Figure 7). They use the car as their daily transport mode and do so rather due to convenience and show below-average concerns about price or environment. The "Busy Green Drivers" differ with putting speed as highest preference and use the car daily in spite of high environmental concerns with regard to traffic pollution. The second biggest group are "Price-Oriented PT-users". They usually use public transport for everyday mobility and give a high importance on price-efficiency but below average importance on the other motives. Among PT-users as well a small group of environmental concerned people, who consider price but even more environmental factors. Pedestrians follow similar grouping features and form price-oriented and green pedestrians. Cyclists mention convenience and speed a bit below average, price above average, but differ in particular in their environmental orientations.

Figure 7: Mobility styles over all countries (own illustration, source: Haustein & Nielsen, 2014)

The mobility styles differ not only in their mode choices and motives, but also in their socio-economic prerequisites. For instance, males are slightly overrepresented among the convenience drivers (55% and 52%) but underrepresented among PT-users and pedestrians. Cyclists are more or less gender balanced. Europeans with a partner are strongly overrepresented among drivers from both types (72.5% Convenience drivers and 71.5% Busy green drivers). Environment and safety as reasons for choosing a mode were only mentioned by as little as around 5% of the participants.

All groups can be found in all European societies but to a different degree. Along the shares of the types, six European country clusters can be identified and are shown in the map in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Country clusters of different mobility styles and motivations (Haustein & Nielsen, 2016)

Cluster 1 combines islands like Ireland or Cyprus with a comparatively weak public transport network and shows a large overrepresentation of convenient drivers and low numbers of cyclists. Green orientations are here rather not considered important in the transport sector.

Similarly, countries from cluster 2 show highest ratios in convenience drivers, but less that in cluster 1. Price-oriented PT users are here the second largest group.

Countries in cluster 3 share high proportions of cyclists as well as green users in all segments. Country cluster 4 show highest numbers in price-oriented PT users and pedestrians. Cluster 5 reflects a high awareness in green topics, that goes hand in hand with a high proportion of green travellers in all modes. Cluster 6 is built by only one country – Hungary has lowest numbers in car users and mostly PT-users or cyclists, that are price- or green oriented. (Haustein, Sonja; Nielsen, Thomas A. Sick (2016)

Countries in cluster 3 share high proportions of cyclists as well as green users in all segments.

Also socio-demographic and economic factors seem to be relevant for the representation of the clusters in a country. So have both car-oriented mobility styles the highest level of socio-economic resources and also a green orientation comes along with higher socio-economic levels. The authors interpret this tendency as the apparent "privilege to choose modes according to motives such as speed and convenience compared to economic affordability [...]" (p. 178, Haustein & Nielsen, 2016).

Based on the representative data from EUROBAROMETER it can be stated, that on an instrumental level, the hierarchy of values differs between the European countries. Additional factors, such as in the first place economic or infrastructural conditions shape mobility preferences. As the authors of the study stated, choosing the mode of transport along personal values and not external restraints must be considered as a privilege (Haustein & Nielsen, 2016). This explanation is also supported by the theory of Ingleharts value shifts between materialism and post materialism as introduced in D3.1. Accordingly, materialist values, here price orientation predominate as long as individuals struggle with fulfilling their basic, security or social needs. Along with a shift of values towards post-materialist values factors like convenience or environmental concerns start rising.

The evaluation of a mode of transport as price-efficient has much to do with the local price policies concerning public transport tickets or fuel- and car taxes. If a mode of transport is considered as speed-efficient, depends on infrastructural circumstances, tempo regulations and priority rules. That includes not only traffic light control or 'green waves' but also road surfaces and quality of connections. In cities for instance with a car priority, the infrastructure is usually optimized for as flawless as possible car traffic flow whereas cities. That in turn influences the perception of the practicability of all modes of transport.

The analysed motivations stem more or less from instrumental considerations, namely speed, price and convenience and added environmental concern but the variety of motivations to be mobile reflect the different behavioural elements of a mobility culture. The ratio of the different mobility styles in a society can reflect in turn the prevailing mobility culture. On the other hand, it can be discussed, if the list of factors is exhaustive. Given the fact, that the first goal of daily mobility must be the instrumental fulfillment of the necessity to be mobile to persevere in life, additional or side values of mobility are often not considered and often lack in mobility surveys. Nevertheless, even this fact may reflect the current narrative as the researchers as well are part of the cultural narrative.

3.2.2 HIDDEN MOTIVES BEHIND MODE CHOICE

The motivations speed and price refer much to communal or state policies. From a subjective point of view, convenience is not as objective, but comprises various other, rather subjective, constructs. The Oxford English Dictionary defines convenience as: "convenience [noun].. the state of being able to proceed with something without difficulty [...] the quality of being useful, easy, or suitable for someone [...] a thing that contributes to an easy and effortless way of life.." ("Convenience", in Oxford Dictionary) These aspects can be found in a study from Belgium by De Vos (2018) with a fairly large sample (N=1,656), that provides us with a more detailed attitude picture, that goes beyond the main motivators over all modes of transport. The study is unique because it enables the comparison of attitudes over all classic transport modes. The studied trips were only leisure trips, following the assumption, that mode and destination choices are more discretionary than mandatory trips e.g. to work.

According to De Vos and his colleagues, the car is perceived as most time saving, closely followed by the bike, and cycling and walking as most inexpensive. When it comes to convenience, cycling, walking and car use are equally, and rather highly pleasant and reliable for most of the participants (see Table 2). Feelings of freedom provided by the modes are highest rated in car use, but also above average in cycling and walking. The leading position holds the car in being comfortable, time saving, private and in the participation in preferred out-of-home activities. The advantages over other modes of transport for PT use are rather small: solely in safety, live quality in the neighbourhood is high rated. This goes in line with a wish among most Europeans, who state, that a better PT-system may solve current traffic problems. The positive aspect ratings for cycling and walking are highest among the studied modes of transport. The bike shows in many aspects pole positions or at least a similarly high rating like car use. In

Table 1. Average scores of positive aspects linked to the use of various travel modes in a Belgian sample (N = 1,656). Derived from De Vos, (2018)

	Car use	PT use	Cycling	Walking
Pleasant	0.62	0.29	0.63	0.67
Good for image	0.20	0.15	0.54	0.34
Environment-friendly	0.00	0.32	0.86	0.77
Relaxing	0.17	0.12	0.67	0.66
Comfortable	0.76	0.14	0.22	0.18
Time saving	0.67	0.09	0.49	0.09
Flexible	0.70	0.05	0.63	0.36
Inexpensive	0.03	0.20	0.82	0.81
Offering privacy	0.76	0.02	0.32	0.28
Healthy	0.02	0.02	0.86	0.83
Safe	0.29	0.43	0.15	0.42
Reliable	0.56	0.15	0.60	0.66
Possibility to perform activities during travel	0.17	0.27	0.15	0.20
Enabling participation in preferred out-of-home activities	0.73	0.16	0.46	0.25
Providing feelings of freedom	0.74	0.09	0.68	0.58
Like to live in neighbourhood stimulating car/PT/cycl./walk	0.70	0.87	0.80	0.80
Total (max. 16)	7.11	3.36	8.87	7.90

inexpensiveness and environmental-friendliness, as well as being good for the image and relaxing it outruns car use. Cycling and walking are perceived as highly environmental friendly. It could be challenged, if that implies, that cyclists are more altruistic, than those who use public transport or even drive a car. However, aspects of cycling like comfort, flexibility, lifestyle and timesavings are the most influential variables on cycling decisions and follow mostly egoistic motives. Beyond that, as well environmental benefits and others (like low costs, health benefits, relaxation) as well play a role in the decisions of commuting by bike. Safety factors like privacy, social safety or traffic safety play a minor role (De Vos, 2018).

The study furthermore indicates, that half of the sample chooses a non-preferred travel mode to reach their leisure destinations. A non-preferred travel mode is when the people rated a particular mode of transport on many dimensions high above the others, but the actual mode choice does not follow this preference. The concept of not using the subjectively preferred mode is called in literature 'Travel mode dissonance' and may lead to dissatisfaction with the chosen mode (de Vos, 2018). In their study, only half of the respondents have chosen their preferred mode of transport. Cyclists made the most congruent choices. More than half of the car users and pedestrians would prefer using another mode of transport with many of them see more positive sides in traveling by bike. Travel mode dissonance appears to be the biggest problem among users of PT; Below average satisfaction levels in PT still lead to a high level of usage and only few users have a stated preference for this mode. The study does not provide data for possible reasons that people behave dissonant, but other studies show, that a consonant trip may lead to a strengthening of positive attitudes towards a mode of transport and therefore to a increased use. But it provides evidence, that not all mode choices happen along stated preference but satisfaction with the trip will be higher in consonant choices.

Following this thought, this may be true for value-consonant mode choices as well. A strong awareness for environmental problems in the last years is stated by about 94% (European Commission, 2020) of all Europeans and already in 2007 a majority of Europeans (74%) thinks, that the type and usage of cars significantly influences the traffic situation in their environment. On the other hand environmental considerations are overall only a minor reason for mode choice behaviour. A willingness to switch to more sustainable modes of transport is in the majority present, but only if it is not more expensive. Additionally, it is supposed to be fast and available. Most willing were younger people with higher education level and rather leftist political position in urban environments. 90% of the Europeans agree on the fact, that the traffic situation needs to be improved and motorized traffic related environmental problems with about 70% of the Europeans that perceived this as important problems. Half of them find that an improved public transport can solve these problems.

Europeans state that they choose their mode if it is convenient, fast and with regard to the price (European Commission, 2014). According to de Vos' study, the car is the absolute leader in comfort, privacy and time savings compared to all other means of transport. This may feed one of the main explanations of the dominance of the cars in the fact, that cars reflect most values from the twentieth-century capitalism and achievements of the industrial revolution such as speed, security, career success, freedom, family and masculinity (Sheller & Urry, 2000; Urry, 2004). Therefore, cities, industries and economy were designed, to make these values be represented in car ownership and driving. Later, Delbosc and Currie (2013) argued, that cars do no longer stand for emancipation and freedom. Their purpose shifts to rather a symbol of responsibility, particularly for those intending to start a family or enter into the labor market. Beyond that, still social pressure from peers or family members can also lead to the getting of the driving licence. Cars can show status but simply owning any car does not directly indicate the affiliation with an upper class. Often, driving a car is the

only option due to a fragmented and unreliable network of public transport, long distances between place of work and place of residence. Decreasing car use since 1990's worldwide among young adults has been observed, especially men (Noble, 2005). There seem to be rather a delay of getting their driving license because of an increasingly functional and utilitarian relationship with cars. (Rérat, Patrick, 2021).

The development of driver license acquisition among young people is a good indicator for changes in societies. Furthermore, as mentioned earlier, if there are changes, it is interesting to note the underlying reasons. In general, a mixed but falling trend in most EU countries can be observed (Sivak & Schoettle, 2012a; Kuhnimhof et al., 2012a). The assumption that cars have lost their position as status symbol is in some countries more true than in others (Delsbosc & Graham, 2013). A major reason in driver license acquisition among young adults can be rooted in changes in household living conditions, such as employment, increase of educational attendance and delayed marriage and parenting (Delbosc & Currie, 2013; Licaj et al., 2012). Furthermore costs for insurance and fuel have increased in the last decade and accessibility due to urbanization made a driver license less mandatory. Whether the last economic recession has its impact on licensing is not clear, as decreases of licensing for instance already decreased before the global financial crisis in 2008 (Davis et al., 2012). Mostly in the developed countries, the likelihood of holding a driver license is lower, than in the last decade. Holding a driver license strengthened for many generations motives like freedom, independence and social status (Steg, 2005). These dimensions are directly connected with basic values like power and self-direction. In EU, the trend seems to be that young adults rather prioritize other activities over acquainting a driver license. A study from Australia shows traces, that showing responsibility became a goal of obtaining a driver license among young adults (Delsbosc & Currie, 2012). This may indicate a real value shift away from power and self-direction towards conformity values, that are served by driving a car. But also contrasting findings are made: In the Netherlands, for instance, young people found to be as likely as their parents in connecting a car with certain status ideals. (Steg, 2005; van der Waard et al., 2013).

Findings from recent studies on multimodal travel behaviour in the US shows that millennials are more willing to use multimodal transport modes compared to older generations. A recent study carried out by global consultancy Duff & Phelps (2019), surveyed 2,150 millennials (people were born between 1980 and 1996) in the U.S. and Canada; Latin America including Mexico, Brazil and Argentina; Europe including Germany, UK, France and Italy; and Asia including China, Hong Kong, Japan, India and Singapore aiming at identifying if they will buy fewer cars than prior generations. For the EU citizens (the UK, France, Germany, and Italy) results indicates that:

- 87% of city dwellers in Europe expect to purchase or lease another car in the next five years,
- 83% of EU millennials believe that having a car is necessity for the perception of independence (77%), convenience (66%) and enjoying while driving as the most important reasons for owning a car
- Italian millennials are more prone (53%) to own hybrid or electric vehicles as they find them more appealing than vehicles with gas or diesel powertrain as the next vehicle compared to other millennials in France, Germany, and the UK.
- Among price, safety, fuel efficiency, and style and look are the role playing features in buying a car, price and fuel efficiency are two top features for millennials in France, Italy and the UK for buying a car. For German millennials, safety is more important feature than fuel

efficiency, in case of Italy and France millennials prefer style and look over safety.

- Using a private car is the first choice for daily travel as the top ranked transport mode for millennials in France, Germany, Italy and the UK
- Almost 80% of millennials in France, Germany and the UK prefer owning or leasing a car over using ride-hailing or car-sharing services if the cost was equal. And in the case of Italian millennials, only 62% prefer to own car instead of using car sharing services.

It should be also noted that understanding behavioural factors influencing young people’s (Generation Z) choices provides a link to future travellers’ way of thinking. The Generation Z travel mode choice today can be regarded as having a formative influence on their travel behaviour as adult.

3.2.3 VALUE OF TIME AS A SUBJECTIVE TRAVEL EXPERIENCE

THE PERCEPTION OF VALUE OF TRAVEL TIME AND VALUE OF RIDESHARING AFFECTS EUROPEANS’ RIDESHARING INTENTION. A CASE STUDY BASED ON MOTIV

A concept that has become a popular concept in recent years among users, mobility authorities, and transport service providers is the sharing of rides as a form of mobility service. A recent study accomplished by Malichova et al. (2020) investigated the influence of users’ perception of Value of Travel Time (VTT) and Value of Ridesharing (VRS) on travellers’ ridesharing participation intention in 4 European countries: Finland, Portugal, Spain, and Slovakia. In results can be seen in case of Portugal, where 38.2% of all respondents prefer to share their rides only with family or friends comparing to 16% as an average from the other three countries. Based on the results from survey, Portuguese people seem to be more cautious when choosing a companion for ridesharing (Figure 9: The intention to adopt ridesharing by country. Figure 9).

Figure 9: The intention to adopt ridesharing by country.

The study results also demonstrate that most people prefer to adopt ridesharing for work compared to other trip purposes (Figure 10). In this case, 21% of all respondents are willing to share their rides only with family or friends and 36% of respondents are willing to adopt ridesharing when commuting to/from

work even with strangers. People prefer to share the rides for the purpose of hobby or leisure during the weekend. Only 21% of respondents are willing to adopt ridesharing during evening trips which may be due to the perception of reduced safety mainly. This survey results also show that the biggest motivator for respondents to share a ride is cost saving or financial benefit (35%). The other two important motivators are easier travel (24%) and helping the environment (22%) (see Figure 11).

Figure 10: Trip purpose to adopt ridesharing.

Finding from this study also reveals that youths (people in age range of 16–24 years) in participant countries preferring to choose ridesharing with strangers given other ridesharing choices which means they are more likely to prefer to share a ride with someone they know or even a stranger compared to having the possibility to share a ride with family.

In regard with companion preferences for ridesharing, it can be noted that Portuguese people seems to be more cautious when choosing a companion for ridesharing (see Figure 9).

The built environment and residing in medium city were also found as significant predictor for being interested in shared rides with others. According to the results, it can be interpreted that people in medium cities, compared to small and metropolitan cities citizens, are more likely willing to participate in a ridesharing with someone they know. When taking into account the perception of gained value regarding the worthwhileness travel time in terms and its impact on choice of ridesharing, results of this study also reveal that people who prefer enjoyment during the traveling are willing to adapt a taxi for ridesharing even with strangers.

Figure 11: Motivators for ridesharing in participant countries.

In the MoTiV project, the value of travel time (VTT) has been assessed based on individuals' subjective travel experience using different transport modes and the evaluation of the perceived level of worthwhileness and perceived mood during trip.

In the MoTiV study, mood ratings were defined as a proxy of the responses to the question "Overall, how did you feel about this trip?" which had a 5-star scale ranging from "Lousy" to "Great". This was the first question users had to answer in the trip validation process, evaluating the whole trip. The mood rating for a trip is given on a scale from 1 (low) to 5 (high) indicating a lousy to a great mood.

Figure 12 illustrates the difference of mood rating between male and female users of different transport modes in 7 European countries. As it can be seen women showed the highest mood rating as the passenger of private cars that is slightly higher than active modes (cycling and walking).

Figure 12: Mood rating differences across transport mode categories by gender.

Worthwhileness ratings also refer to trip legs performed by specific transport modes and the 5-star scale ranged from “All time was wasted” to “All time was worthwhile”. Figure 13. illustrates the travellers’ perceived level of worthwhileness of travel time using various transport modes across different countries.

Figure 13: Travel time worthwhileness rating differences across transport mode categories by gender.

Travel time worthwhileness average rating across 9 European countries as shown in Figure 14, indicate some differences among countries. For instance, in Italy, Slovakia and Croatia in average people had a higher perception of travel time worthwhileness compare to Finish, Spanish and Belgian travellers.

Figure 14: Travel time worthwhileness average rating across 9 European countries.

Figure 15 also presents the distribution of the four types of worthwhileness per each value of worthwhileness element for all respondents across transport mode categories by gender. Results elucidate that for all the worthwhileness elements, the majority of people travelling by motorized mode transport reported enjoyment and ability to do personal task while on move as the most important gained value for their travel time. As expected for the active modes, men and women reported fitness (ability do exercise) as the most worthwhile value perceived during travel time.

Figure 15: Distribution of four types of worthwhileness values across transport mode categories by gender.

During travelling, travellers experience differences in the worthwhileness while using the different modes of transport. The MoTiV project gathered a total of 48 different experience factors for which users could report a positive or negative contribution to the perceived quality of travel time.

The two tables below present the top 20 most frequently selected experience factors contributing positively or negatively in the users genuine travel experience.

Table 2 Top 20 positive experience factors reported by users affecting the perceived value of travel time

Positive factors	Modes for which experience factor was available
Simplicity/difficulty of the route	all
Today's Weather	all
Ability to do what I want	all
Scenery	all
Reliability of travel time	all
Road path availability & safety	Active modes
Road path directness	Active modes
Road path quality	Active & Private motorised
Noise level	all
Parking at end points	Cycling & Private motorised
Air quality	all
Security & Safety	PT & Private motorised
Other people	PT & Active modes
Route planning & navigation tools	all
Information & signs	all
Ability to take kids or pets along	all
Convenient access	PT
Vehicle quality	Private motorised
Lighting /Visibility	Active modes
Privacy	PT & Private motorised

Based on the reported positive experience factors (Table 2), it is observed that quite a few of them relate to transport services and infrastructure such as the road path availability, quality and directness, reliability, parking, information and signs or route planning and navigation tools.

The top 20 experience factors European travellers reported to have a negative contribution to the perceived value of travel time across five transport mode categories is also shown in Table 3. An additional feature presented at this table is the indication of unwanted efforts next to each experience factor that was rated negatively. Unwanted efforts are external stressors that prevent engaging into worthwhile activities and can be categorised as follows:

- Physical (p) is an effort asked of and imposed on the body in undertaking travel such as having to stand in a crowded bus or go upstairs;
- Cognitive (c) effort is the mental focus that is needed to execute the journey successfully e.g. noisy or attention demanding environment (unwanted distractions, difficulty to plan trip or know where to go), and;

- Affective (a) is the emotional influence of undertaking the journey i.e. stressful, unsafe or unreliable.

Table 3 Top 20 negative experience factors reported by users affecting the perceived value of travel time

Negative Factors (& Category of Unwanted Efforts)	Modes for which experience factor was available
Noise level (c)	all
Air quality (a)	all
Cars/Other vehicles (c)	Active & Private motorised
Today's Weather (a)	all
Scenery (a)	all
Road path availability & Safety (a)	Active modes
Road path quality (c)	Active & Private motorised
Crowding/Congestion (p)	Active modes
Ability to do what I wanted (c)	all
Traffic congestion/ delays (a)	Private motorised
Other people (c)	PT & Active modes
Traffic signals/Crossings (a)	Active modes
Simplicity/Difficulty of the route (c)	all
Reliability of travel time (a)	all
Ability to take kids or pets along (p)	all
Facilities/Shower/Lockers (a)	Active modes
Charging opportunity (a)	PT & Private motorised
Convenient access (p)	PT
Information & signs (c)	all
Privacy (c)	PT & Private motorised

4 INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY AND ITS IMPACT ON MOBILITY

The role and importance of ICT in mobility has been investigated from different perspectives and in various disciplines including philosophy, the social sciences and human computer interaction.

In the last few decades, a wide range of studies have also been carried out by transport researchers, mobility planners and policy makers to explore the role of ICT, particularly smartphones and tablets on changing and shaping people travel behaviour using different transport services not only for the conventional transport planning but also for the emerging mobility systems such as micro-mobility systems, shared mobility services (e.g. carpooling, car sharing, crowd sourced micro-task deliveries), Mobility as a Service (MaaS) and Automated Vehicles (AVs).

As outlined by several scholars (Lee & Circella, 2019; Gössling, 2018; Cohen-Blankshtain & Rotem-Mindali, 2016 and Snellen & de Hollander, 2017) there is a considerable evidence that digital personal devices strongly influence mobility and activity patterns of individuals across cultures, generations and gender. This fact is also increasingly exploited to promote more sustainable behaviours, well-being and life balance.

In this regard, the results of EU-funded projects that have investigated the influence of ICT on changing value proposition mobility from different perspectives. In following findings from 2 EU projects MoTiv11, and MyCorridor13 regarding the Value of Travel

Time (VTT) beyond the time and Cost saving, car sharing and Mobility as a Service (MaaS) concepts.

Results from MyCorridor five pilot sites (Figure 16) illustrate the differences among different gender and age ranges in terms of using online journey planners. As can be seen Men are more often using the online services in 4 surveyed EU countries except in Italy. Not surprisingly, results also indicates the tendency of young people in the age range 25-49 on using more often online platforms for daily mobility planning compare to age groups in 4 surveyed EU countries Austria, Czech republic, Greece , Italy and the Netherland. It is also worth noting that survey results indicate the significant penetration of ICT for daily mobility planning across all age groups in the Netherlands.

Figure 16: Gender difference in using online mobility services platforms

Figure 17: Difference in use of online mobility services platforms by different age groups

Transport planners and policymakers often hope that ICT could reduce the need for travel and to some extent substitute people’s non-obligatory daily trips. Although there has been a big uncertainty about the travel substitution.

In following, results from the MoTiV project have been illustrated which highlight that most frequent ICT-related activities people carried while on move in short urban trips (less than 30km) using various transport modes in 8 European countries (Belgium, Italy, Finland, France, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, and Slovakia) across different age groups and genders.

Figure 18. Number of ICT activities carried out by traveller in different age ranges during travel based on transport different mode categories

As can be seen in Figure 18, people in age range of 16-24 prefer to browse during active travel. It brings them some form of enjoyment and it is not related to fulfilling work tasks, which is also confirmed by the high frequency of listening.

In the case of public transport, passengers are mainly browsing or listening while travelling for almost age groups (Figure 18). It can be also noted that the most frequent ICT related activity for people in age range of 50-64 is listening to audio (e.g. music, book).

Figure 19. Number of ICT activities carried out by women and men during travel based on different transport mode categories

Figure 19 shows the numbers of ICT activities performed during urban travels by gender across different transport modes. According to the MoTIV results, there is no significant difference between the ICT-related activities performed by women and men across different transport modes. Although, the results imply a common pattern and high tendency of using ICT devices for browsing internet while traveling by public transport among men and women. The distribution of frequency for using ICT devices for 4 predefined activities: browsing internet, listening to audio, e-reading and watching video by men and women have been shown in Figure 20.

4.1 ICT ACTIVITIES THAT ARE MORE FREQUENTLY ASSOCIATED WITH WORTHWHILENESS RATINGS

As a part of MoTiV which captured respondents' perception of value of travel time in terms of being totally wasted or worthwhile (satisfactory) in a scale from 1 (time was wasted) to 5 (time was worthwhile), Worthwhileness of travel time was measured by the question "Was your travel time wasted or worthwhile?". Travellers could evaluate their travel time on a 5-point scale in which point 1 meant "All time was wasted" and point 5 meant "All time was worthwhile". The correlation between the travellers' perception of travel time worthwhileness and the performed ICT-related activities among gender and different age groups for urban trips less than 30 KMs have been illustrated in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Figure 21: Correlation between average worthwhileness rating and ICT activities by gender

Figure 20: Correlation between average worthwhileness rating and ICT activities by different age groups.

were also identified in browsing. Men who browsed the Internet while travelling rated travel time as more worthwhile than women, and vice versa, men who watched videos or movies while travelling considered their travel time less worthwhile than women.

Figure 21 shows a comparison of average worthwhileness rating related to ICT activities for all respondents and by age groups for urban trips less than 30 Kms. As can be seen, it is also evident that overall people reading on electronic devices while travelling evaluate their travel time as the most worthwhile. When comparing the results based on age groups, in the case of reading on electronic devices there is a significant difference in evaluating worthwhileness.

Figure 22: Number of ICT activities carried out by male travelers during travel based on the level of worthwhileness factors (enjoyment, productivity, and fitness)

Figure 23: Number of ICT activities carried out by female travelers during travel based on the level of worthwhileness factors (enjoyment, productivity, and fitness)

When comparing the results based on age groups (Figure 21) in the case of reading on electronic devices there is a significant difference in evaluating worthwhileness among different age groups.

Figure 23 and Figure 22 show the numbers of ICT activities performed during travel by gender. No significant difference was identified between the activities performed by men and women and their assessment of worthwhileness factors.

4.2 DOES TELECOMMUNICATION SUBSTITUTE TRAVEL NEED? INSIGHTS FROM THE PANDEMIC.

In the last decades, extensive empirical studies have been accomplished regarding the role of ICT on travel behaviour and its potential impacts on individuals’ mobility pattern in terms of modification, substitution, and enhancement of or acceleration (Konrad and Wittkowski, 2018).

In respect of the substitution, saving travel and reducing non-mandatory trips, even when is feasible, ICT is not always a desirable substitute as stated by Mokhtarian (2009). As such it is not possible to entirely substitute some certain type of activities which need the co-location of human being despite vast efforts on minimizing or reducing the demand for physical participation in activities (Figure 24). As noted by Kuller and Moragillio (2020), it is evident that ICT completely overthrown former certainties regarding needs, desires and motivations to move or not and people’s potential movement is currently reliant on access and, personal aptitude and skills the use of ICT.

For many years there were challenging arguments by scholars and transport planners concerning the possibility of replacing physical activities participation with virtual ones such as teleworking, e-learning, online shopping and participation in online art events (e.g., concerts, theatre and movies) through various livestream platforms which could extensively contribute to reducing traffic congestion in urban networks and abating adverse environmental impact of road transport. Although the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak emergency imposed sudden changes in lifestyle and the corporeal mobility routines of millions of people, but it was an unexpected opportunity for amplifying the need for and use of information and communication technologies. The pandemic has

also brought trial opportunities for people to experience not only teleworking and e-learning but also virtual participation in leisure activities such as online art events (e.g., concerts, watching theatre and movies) through various livestream platforms.

A recent study on the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on Italian young people’s lifestyle and leisure activities by Panarese & Azzarita (2021) reveals a significant increase in online participation in a variety of activities by the youngest age group. The study results also accentuated the higher interest of female respondents in participation in webinars or online tutorials, using social media and messaging services and communication through chat and video-chatting services while males were more interested in playing online games.

Figure 24: Schematic relationship among activities involving travel and those involving ICT (adapted from Mokhtarian, 2009).

Despite the fact that the ICT proliferation is constantly changing corporeal mobility needs in daily life for all age ranges and social distancing due the COVID-19 pandemic also reformed extensively citizens’ mobility behaviour, but from a general scientific perspective the virtual life cannot be replaced the face to face contacts, physical socialization and engaging in activities require co-presence in long-term and virtual mobility would not also utterly substitute individuals’ physical movements in particular demand for business travels as argued by Aguilera and Proulhace (2015).

5 CONCLUSIONS

The report has shown, that the car is still a ‘best practice’ in fulfilling a wide range of values far beyond the instrumental motives of being mobile. Energized by ICT and innovative concepts of sharing rides and vehicles, multimodality becomes more and more easy to access. It connects different travel modes with each other and make it easy to access and combine the most convenient, fast and price-efficient modes.

In the analysis of mode choice and values above, one inconsistency is inignorable: The attitudes towards different modes, in particular walking, driving and cycling but also towards sharing tell another story than actually measured behavioural data indicates. Following, the willingness and ability to use more environmental friendly modes of transport seems to be quite high in European Union. People are well aware of the problems induced by their mobility choices and often not even behave according to their values and attitudes. Also they state a willingness to change behaviour, but the advantages attributed to the car are still strong and are all best tuned to automobility. Instrumental goals combined post-material motives such as promotion of self-

actualization and self-esteem and are still connected with car use that reflects independence and high levels of convenience with using a car. If this car needs to be possessed or could be shared is debatable.

The creation of space in almost all European countries follow the idea of perfecting instrumental, hedonic and individual values, but with a strong focus on the car usage. The analysis showed, that other modes of transport, and in particular the bicycle, can fulfill similarly high levels of post-materialist needs and values like the car. About one century politics and industries developed a system, which indeed makes the car most convenient and often even cost-effective for everyday-trips. This narrative fits the strength of the industrial sector which stands for power and progress. The rise of the importance around altruistic values begins to move the self-actualization needs in a new direction. Self-actualization in the young generation more and more can mean to consume more cautious for environment and society. The car as a costume that stands for the social function of the car to show distinction and the opportunity to express oneself (Schlag and Schade, 2007), may need to lose meaning for the younger generation.

Based on users' experience and the positive and negative factors influencing their mode of transport choice, the analysis of experience factors can be essential to promote alternative modes to private motorised transport, like cycling and public transport.

Although, there is wide political scope for improving the experience factors that were rated negatively in direct comparison:

- For public transport, planners and operators should try to avoid overcrowding, increasing passenger capacity and service frequency wherever possible. It is important to ensure that as much privacy as possible is given to passengers, providing silent spaces for activities requiring concentration like reading or working, especially on long-distance public transport.
- Given the constant changes in travel patterns, user perception on travel modes and emerging mobility services, gathering and analysing data regarding these changes is necessary to tackle existing transport and mobility challenges to support a more efficient and human-centred sustainable transport system.
- Environmental concern as well as the problem perception of Europeans about the consequences in particular of the car are high. However, so far this does not really translate into behaviour like mode choice. As already identified in Deliverable 3.1 pro-social and environmental values rather do not show a direct effect on behaviour but an indirect effect via the acceptance of policies to mitigate the negative consequences of transport.

All sectors in Europe are not only moving towards climate sustainability, but also to a greater integration within digital technologies. Transport planners should take into account the widespread use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) while travelling. For instance, MoTiV found that listening to audio and browsing the Internet are the most frequent ICT-related activities performed. In the case of public transport, passengers are mainly browsing the internet or listening to audio while travelling, which may be due to the availability of Wi-Fi on board. In the case of public transport, passengers are mainly browsing or listening while travelling, meaning that this mode of transport could gain in attractiveness from facilitating these activities, for

example by providing internet access and charging opportunities. Two other activities that were associated with high worthwhileness ratings were reading electronic devices for men and watching films or videos for women. In order to increase attractiveness of public transport modes, operators could therefore consider providing a small selection of free and/or pay-on-demand e-books and movies/series via the vehicle's WiFi network.

The results of the analysis of existing academic and European research and innovation projects clearly show that mobility planning needs to be reconsidered in favour of travellers' needs and expectations. Maximising the perceived value proposition of mobility and worthwhileness of travel time, as a part of the subjective theory of value should also be considered as a crucial driver for a paradigm shift on transport planning and policies striving travellers' satisfaction beyond the time- and cost saving and overemphasis of the travel speed (Banister et al., 2019). Therefore, it is pivotal to make the case that from a traveller perspective, the experience of travel time does matter which can place the user experience in a central role in transport planning. They bring important insights for conventional transport planning and assessment tools that are currently based on more simplified set of variables such as travel costs and absolute timesavings on mode-specific portions of door-to-door trips.

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6 REFERENCES

Aguilera, Anne; Proulhac, Laurent (2015). Socio-occupational and geographical determinants of the frequency of long-distance business travel in France, *Journal of Transport Geography*, Volume 43, 2015, Pages 28-35, ISSN 0966-6923, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2015.01.004>

Banister, David (2019). Transport for all. In: *Transport Reviews* 39 (3), S. 289–292. DOI: 10.1080/01441647.2019.1582905

Bastian, A., Börjesson, M., Eliasson, J. (2016). Explaining “peak car” with economic variables. *Transportation Research Part A*, 88 236–250.

Davis, B., T. Dutzik and P. Baxandall (2012). Transportation and the new generation: why young people are driving less and what it means for transportation policy, Frontier Group.

Delbosc, Alexa; Currie, Graham (2013). Causes of Youth Licensing Decline: A Synthesis of Evidence. In: *Transport Reviews* 33 (3), S. 271–290. DOI: 10.1080/01441647.2013.801929

De Vos, J. (2018). Do people travel with their preferred travel mode? Analysing the extent of travel mode dissonance and its effect on travel satisfaction. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 117, 261–274. DOI: 10.1016/j.tra.2018.08.034

Duff & Phelps Study (2019). Will Millennials Drive the Automotive Industry Forward? <https://www.duffandphelps.ca/-/media/assets/pdfs/publications/mergers-and-acquisitions/will-millennials-drive-automotive-industry-forward.pdf>

ESS Round 9: European Social Survey Round 9 Data (2018). Data file edition 3.1. NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data, Norway – Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC. DOI: 10.21338/NSD-ESS9-2018

European Commission. (2007). Flash Eurobarometer 206b—Attitudes on Issues related to EU Transport Policy. European Commission.

European Commission. (2013). Special Eurobarometer 406—Attitudes of Europeans towards urban mobility. European Commission.

European Commission. (2014). Special Eurobarometer 422a—Quality of Transport. European Commission.

European Commission. (2020). Special Eurobarometer 495 – Mobility and Transport. European Commission.

European Commission. (2020). Special Eurobarometer 501—Attitudes of European citizens towards the Environment. European Commission.

Focas, C., Christidis, P. (2017). Peak Car in Europe?. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 25, 531-550

Fraboni, Federico; Prati, Gabriele; Casu, Giulia; Angelis, Marco de; Pietrantonio, Luca (2021). A cluster analysis of cyclists in Europe: common patterns, behaviours, and attitudes. In: *Transportation*. DOI: 10.1007/s11116-021-10187-3

Gatersleben, Birgitta; Uzzell, David (2007): Affective Appraisals of the Daily Commute. In: *Environment and Behavior* 39 (3), S. 416–431. DOI: 10.1177/0013916506294032

Goodwin, P. (2011). Three views on 'Peak Car'. *World Transport Policy Pract.* 17 (4).

Haustein, Sonja; Nielsen, Thomas A. Sick (2016). European mobility cultures: A survey-based cluster analysis across 28 European countries. In: *Journal of Transport Geography* 54, Pp. 173–180. DOI: 10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2016.05.014

Konrad, Kathrin; Wittowsky, Dirk (2018). Virtual mobility and travel behavior of young people – Connections of two dimensions of mobility, *Research in Transportation Economics*, Vol. 68, Pp. 11-17. ISSN 0739-8859, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2017.11.002>

Konings, Herman; Van der Dist Konings, Stefaan (2015). MIND-SETS: A Generational Perspective on Mobility. Deliverable 2.1c of the MIND-SETS

Project. European Commission Directorate General for Research, Covent Garden, Brussels.

Kuhnimhof, T., Armoogum, J., Buehler, R., Dargay, J., Denstadli, J.M., Yamamoto, T. (2012). Men shape a downward trend in car use among young adults—evidence from six industrialized countries. *Transport Rev.* 32 (6), 761–779.

Kuttler, T., & Moraglio, M. (Eds.). (2020). *Re-thinking Mobility Poverty: Understanding Users' Geographies, Backgrounds and Aptitudes* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780367333317>

Licaj, I., Haddak, M., Pochet, P., & Chiron, M. (2012). Individual and contextual socioeconomic disadvantages and car driving between 16 and 24 years of age: a multilevel study in the Rhône Département (France). *Journal of transport geography*, 22, 19-27.

Malichova, E., Pourhashem, G., Kováčiková, T. and Hudák, M. (2020). Users' Perception of Value of Travel Time and Value of Ridesharing impacts on Europeans' ridesharing participation intention: a case study based on MoTiV European-wide mobility and behavioural pattern dataset, *Sustainability journal*, 12(10), 4118. DOI: 10.3390/su12104118

Metz, D. (2010). Saturation of demand for daily travel. *Transport Rev.* 30 (5), 659–674.

Metz, D. (2013). Peak car and beyond: the fourth era of travel. *Transport Rev.* 33 (3), 255–270.

Miller, D. (Ed.). (2020). *Car cultures*. Routledge.

Mokhtarian, Patricia (2009). If telecommunication is such a good substitute for travel, why does congestion continue to get worse?, *Transportation Letters*, 1:1, 1-17, DOI: 10.3328/TL.2009.01.01.1-17

Noble, B. (2005). *Why are Some Young People Choosing Not to Drive?* Strasbourg: European Transport Conference.

Panarese , Vittoria Azzarita (2021). The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Lifestyle: How Young people have Adapted Their Leisure and Routine during Lockdown in Italy , Volume: 29 issue: 4_suppl, page(s): S35-S64, DOI: 10.1177/11033088211031389.

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/11033088211031389>

Prieto, Marc; Baltas, George; Stan, Valentina (2017). Car sharing adoption intention in urban areas: What are the key sociodemographic drivers?. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 101(), 218–227. DOI:10.1016/j.tra.2017.05.012

Ramos, Érika Martins Silva; Bergstad, Cecilia Jakobsson; Chicco, Andrea; Diana, Marco (2020). Mobility styles and car sharing use in Europe: attitudes, behaviours, motives and sustainability. In: *Eur. Transp. Res. Rev.* 12 (1). DOI: 10.1186/s12544-020-0402-4

Rérat, Patrick (2021). A decline in youth licensing: a simple delay or the decreasing popularity of automobility? In: *Applied Mobilities* 6 (1), S. 71–91. DOI: 10.1080/23800127.2018.1545737

Rodenbach, Johannes; Mathis, Jeffrey; Chicco, Andrea; Diana, Marco (2020). STARS: Car Sharing in Europe. Deliverable 2.1 of the STARS Project. European Commission Directorate General for Research, Covent Garden, Brussels.

Schlag, Bernhard; Schade, Jens (2007). *Psychologie des Verkehrsverhaltens*. In: *APUZ Aus Politik und Zeitgeschichte: Verkehrspolitik* (29-30), S. 17–32.

Schwartz, Shalom H. (2012). An Overview of the Schwartz Theory of Basic Values. In: *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture* 2 (1). DOI: 10.9707/2307-0919.1116

Sheller, Mimi; Urry, John (2006). The New Mobilities Paradigm. In: *Environ Plan A* 38 (2), S. 207–226. DOI: 10.1068/a37268

Steg, L. (2005). Car use: lust and must. Instrumental, symbolic and affective motives for car use. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 39(2-3), 147-162.

van Wee, B. (2015). Peak car: the first signs of a shift towards ICT-based activities replacing travel? A discussion paper. *Transport Policy*, 42, 1–3.

Zhou, M., Wang, D. (2019). Generational differences in attitudes towards car, car ownership and car use in Beijing. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 72, 261-278.

